

IMPLEMENTATION OF LOCAL WISDOM IN SUPPORTING CRITICAL THINKING-BASED LEARNING FOR ELEMENTARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

Basic education in Indonesia requires a learning approach that can foster students' critical thinking skills in a more meaningful way, especially since some schools still rely on conventional methods that do not provide enough space for analysis, evaluation, and active student participation. A literature review shows that the integration of local wisdom can enrich the learning context so that students can more easily connect the material with their daily experiences while understanding cultural values that are relevant to their lives. In addition, previous studies have confirmed that culture-based Project-Based Learning can encourage the development of analytical, argumentative, collaborative, and creative skills, as well as problem-solving through real activities that are close to the students' socio-cultural environment. This study uses the Systematic Literature Review method to examine articles discussing the implementation of local wisdom in supporting critical thinking-based learning in elementary school students. Data collection was conducted through Google Scholar with the criteria of articles published between 2012 and 2025, relevant to the topic, and meeting academic quality standards. The analysis stages included identification, selection, assessment of article quality, information extraction, and synthesis of findings. The synthesis results show that the application of local cultural elements through field observations, value discussions, community projects, traditional games, and the creation of cultural products can improve students' analytical, interpretive, creative, and logical reasoning skills. The Project-Based Learning model that raises local themes also provides authentic experiences that stimulate higher-order thinking skills and increase learning motivation. In addition to strengthening cognitive abilities, the integration of local wisdom also contributes to the formation of students' character, cultural identity, empathy, and social awareness. Thus, local wisdom is an important component in realizing contextual, critical, and relevant learning in line with the demands of 21st-century education.

Keywords: *wisdom, local, students, learning, critical.*

INTRODUCTION

Basic education in Indonesia is currently undergoing a transformation that requires the application of more meaningful teaching methods, appropriate to the context, and focused on developing 21st-century skills. Although the 2013 Curriculum and the Merdeka Curriculum emphasize the importance of critical thinking skills, many schools still rely on conventional approaches such as lectures. This results in students lacking the skills to analyze data and solve problems independently. In addition, the low critical thinking skills among Indonesian students are also influenced by strong cultural factors, such as the tendency to rely on teachers as the main source of information, as well as social norms such as "manut lan miturut" and "ewuh pakewuh" which discourage students from asking questions and expressing their opinions (Maro, 2016).

In this context, local wisdom emerges as an appropriate approach to be integrated into the learning process. Indonesia has a rich cultural heritage that can be used as contextual teaching material, enabling students to connect their learning with their social and cultural environment. Teaching methods based on local wisdom not only strengthen cultural identity but also have the potential to improve critical thinking skills through observation, analysis, reflection, and evaluation activities derived from students' direct experiences (Amirin MT, 2012).

Several previous studies have shown that incorporating local wisdom into the learning process can improve students' critical thinking skills. (Putu Yustika Rini et al., 2023) found that teaching methods related to local cultural practices encourage students to analyze phenomena more deeply. (also states that a learning environment based on everyday culture helps students to observe, assess, and draw conclusions independently. Similar findings were reported by (Nuril et al., 2024), which showed that combining Project-Based Learning (PjBL) with elements of local culture strengthens students' exploration, collaboration, and problem-solving skills.

Based on this, it is important to examine how the application of local wisdom can support learning that emphasizes critical thinking in elementary schools, especially when combined with the PjBL model that highlights project activities and problem solving. The use of PjBL based on local wisdom is expected to create learning experiences that are relevant to the context and analytical, as shown by research emphasizing the link between culture-based learning and improved critical thinking skills (Erdalina Sinulinggal et al., 2025). Therefore, this study was conducted to provide a theoretical and practical overview of the approach to applying local wisdom in supporting critical thinking-based learning in Indonesian elementary education.

RESEARCH PROBLEM

Learning in elementary schools is still largely dominated by methods that emphasize memorization and one-way delivery of material, so that students rarely have the opportunity to independently develop their analytical, evaluative, and critical thinking skills. Meanwhile, local wisdom, which is rich in values, practices, and authentic experiences, has not been optimally utilized as a learning resource that can strengthen higher-order thinking processes. This problem becomes more prominent when most schools only include cultural elements superficially, without truly integrating them into learning activities that require problem solving and deep reasoning, so that the potential of local wisdom as a contextual learning tool cannot be fully developed. Based on this situation, the research question in this study is how the implementation of local wisdom can be designed and carried out to strengthen critical thinking-based learning for elementary school students. Therefore, this study aims to explain the stages, activities, and forms of effective application of local wisdom in encouraging students' critical thinking skills.

RESEARCH METHOD

This study applies the Systematic Literature Review (SLR) method by referring to the framework of the "PRISMA 2020", which facilitates researchers to systematically review previous studies to identify patterns, findings, and approaches to implementing local wisdom in supporting critical thinking-oriented learning at the elementary school level (Snyder, 2019). This method was chosen based on its ability to analyze research themes in depth through scientific documents such as journal articles and books without the need to collect data in the field. In addition, SLR provides an organized analytical framework so that the results of the study are more thorough and comprehensive (Amirin MT, 2012).

The search for sources was conducted through the Google Scholar platform using key words such as "local wisdom," "critical thinking," "Project-Based Learning," and "elementary school learning." Publication restrictions were applied to the 2012–2025 period to ensure the relevance of the sources to curriculum development and basic education practices in Indonesia. Selected articles must demonstrate focus relevance, full accessibility, and contain empirical or conceptual data related to the application of local wisdom and the development of students' critical thinking skills. Several articles that meet the criteria and are used as primary references include a study by (Putu Yustika Rini et al., 2023) which examines culture-based learning,

(Nuril et al., 2024) which integrates Project-Based Learning (PjBL) with local wisdom, (which examines PjBL based on Papuan culture, as well as(M. Rino Ryad Raekhan et al., 2025) and (Erdalina Sinulingga1 et al., 2025) which explores the relationship between local culture and critical thinking skills.

Data analysis was carried out through four main stages, namely: intensive reading, identification of crucial information, grouping of findings, and synthesis of patterns between studies. This synthesis process mapped aspects such as the forms of local wisdom implementation, the parties involved, the learning context applied, the timing of the cultural approach, the reasons for the effectiveness of local wisdom in encouraging critical thinking, and the learning implementation mechanisms in previous studies (Putu Yustika Rini et al., 2023). At this stage, Project-Based Learning (PjBL) is treated as a literature finding, not as a research method, given its use by several researchers to incorporate local cultural activities into the learning process (Risamasu & Pieter, 2024).

The synthesized results from all articles were then used to formulate a comprehensive overview of effective local wisdom implementation strategies in strengthening critical thinking-based learning for elementary school students. Using the SLR approach, this study successfully produced a systematic, in-depth review that is relevant to the context of Indonesian elementary education (M. Rino Ryad Raekhan et al., 2025).

RESULTS

NO	Focus of Local Wisdom Implementation	Form of Learning Activities	Findings Related to Critical Thinking
1	Science based on local culture - example: students study the process of "Nyaken" (traditional Balinese brown sugar making) to understand changes in the form of substances and heat reactions.	Environmental observation, experiments based on local culture	Students are able to analyze cultural phenomena and provide scientific explanations

2	Thematic learning based on local culture - example: exploring the "Mapalus" ceremony of Minahasa as a practice of cooperation, then students assess its relevance in the modern era.	Traditional exploration, discussion, presentation	Improving students' critical thinking and independence skills
3	Strengthening cultural values in classroom activities - case study on the "Marsialapari" tradition (Batak mutual assistance), analyzed to examine its social function.	Local case studies, reflection, value discussions	Strengthening reasoning, evaluation, and problem-solving skills
4	PjBL on Papuan traditions — example: field investigation of "Honai" (traditional Papuan houses), analyzing design and environmental reasons.	Field investigation, cultural project	Improving in-depth analysis, argumentation, and reasoning
5	K-13 strategy based on cultural values — example: analyzing the folk tale "Timun Mas" to identify conflicts, solutions, and moral values.	HOTS exercises based on local culture	Developing analysis and generalization skills
6	Multicultural education based on local wisdom — example: comparing the	Discussion of cultural values & local context	Encouraging critical and evaluative perspectives

	Javanese greeting tradition ("sungkem") and the Bugis tradition ("mappasiluka") to learn about the value of respect.		
7	Culture-based project-based learning (PJBL) — example: a project mapping the cultural potential of a village (local batik, traditional cuisine, regional dances).	Community project report	Students are able to interpret cultural data, think logically, and draw conclusions
8	PjBL and critical thinking — example: problem-solving projects based on cultural issues such as preserving folk tales that are beginning to disappear.	Problem-based projects, group presentations	Improving students' analytical, evaluative, and scientific argumentation skills
9	Character education based on local wisdom — example: reflection on the Javanese value of "tepa selira" in students' social interactions.	Discussion of cultural values, character reflection	Strengthening critical thinking skills while shaping character and social attitudes
10	Meta-analysis of local wisdom for critical thinking — example: synthesis of studies on local wisdom such as Saman dance, Dayak culture, Balinese rituals, and Sundanese wisdom.	Literature review of various studies	Demonstrating the significant influence of local wisdom on improving students' critical thinking skills

DISCUSSION

Local wisdom plays an important role in basic education because it provides a learning context that is close to students' lives, making the material more relevant and easier to understand. Local cultural elements, such as folk tales, daily traditions, traditional ceremonies, and social practices, can be used as learning resources to train students' observation, analysis, and evaluation skills (Putu Yustika Rini et al., 2023); (M. Rino Ryad Raekhan et al., 2025). The integration of cultural elements encourages students to think critically by comparing cultural values, assessing their relevance in a modern context, and drawing conclusions based on their own observations (Erdalina Sinulingga1 et al., 2025). This approach not only adds depth to the material but also makes students more active and creative in the learning process.

The use of PjBL based on local wisdom has proven effective in developing critical thinking skills. In this activity, students are directly involved in projects that require them to collect data, make observations, compile reports, and present their findings. For example, students can learn about local traditions through field investigations or create cultural products as group projects, so that they learn to analyze, assess, and solve problems independently (Risamasu & Pieter, 2024). A literature review by (Jeniver1 et al., 2023) confirms that culture-based PjBL improves students' analytical skills, reasoning abilities, and scientific argumentation. Thus, PjBL provides a contextual learning experience while encouraging students to think critically in a systematic manner.

In addition to improving critical thinking skills, learning based on local wisdom also strengthens students' character and social values. Character education that integrates local culture helps students develop empathy, tolerance, and multicultural awareness (Faiz & Soleh, 2021) . For example, through discussions of cultural values and reflections on social practices, students learn to assess different perspectives and understand the meaning of cultural practices in everyday life. This is in line with the findings (Amirin MT, 2012) which state that multicultural education based on local wisdom can foster reflective and evaluative perspectives, so that students not only assess information but are also able to consider various points of view in decision-making.

The results of meta-analysis and literature synthesis show that local wisdom has a significant influence on improving the critical thinking skills of elementary school students (Ristiani et al., 2024). The integration of local culture through PjBL, community projects, value reflection, and discussion activities provides contextual, analytical, and comprehensive learning experiences. Students learn to think systematically, interpret information, construct logical arguments, and design creative solutions. Thus, the application of local wisdom not only strengthens cognitive abilities but also shapes students' character, cultural identity, and multicultural awareness. This strategy is in line with the goals of 21st-century education, which emphasizes the development of critical, creative, and character-building thinking skills in the context of the local socio-cultural environment.

CONCLUSION

The implementation of local wisdom in elementary school learning has proven to be effective in improving students' critical thinking skills. Cultural elements, such as traditions, folklore, traditional ceremonies, social practices, and local values, provide a learning context that is real and close to students' lives. By using familiar and relevant material, students find it easier to observe phenomena, analyze information, evaluate facts, and draw conclusions independently. This process not only helps students understand the material more deeply, but also trains their ability to think logically, compare different perspectives, and solve problems in a systematic way.

The use of the Project-Based Learning (PjBL) model combined with local wisdom provides an active, analytical, and comprehensive learning experience. Through field investigations, data collection, report writing, and presentations, students can learn about local traditions, create cultural products, or research local community practices as group projects. These activities encourage them to think critically, interpret information, construct logical arguments, and design creative solutions to real problems in their environment. Thus, project-based learning not only improves cognitive skills but also builds learning independence and students' ability to think analytically and systematically.

Beyond cognitive aspects, integrating local wisdom into learning also helps shape students' character, cultural identity, and multicultural awareness. Through cultural value reflection, discussion, and character education reinforcement, students learn to appreciate social diversity,

understand different perspectives, and develop empathy and tolerance. These activities train students to assess situations from various points of view, make appropriate decisions, and understand the meaning of cultural practices in everyday life. Overall, learning based on local wisdom not only improves critical thinking skills but also prepares students to become individuals with character, cultural knowledge, and readiness to face the challenges of 21st-century education.

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